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LITERATURE REVIEW OF CYSTIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS

SURVEILLANCE AND CONTROL

MACE is a project that aims to provide a portfolio of surveillance options and control interventions for cystic echinococcosis that is evaluated to be the most efficient and effective. This project will combine economic evaluations of surveillance and control options available with a mathematical model that will be developed to simulate the transmission dynamics of cystic echinococcosis to analyse the impact and cost-effectiveness. This report describes the literature on cystic echinococcosis and the methods available for control and monitoring in both animals and humans; It includes a review on the transmission of the disease, the diagnosis and treatment options, prevention and intervention methods, and a discussion of the existing mathematical models of disease transmission transmission.

This written report was used as the introductory (first) chapter of the “confirmation report”, a document required for all PhD students after their first year at UoS.

1.1 - Introduction

Cystic Echinococcosis (CE) is a zoonotic disease caused by the metacestode (echinococcal cyst) of the tapeworm *Echinococcus granulosus*, which belongs to the family Taeniidae [1]. CE is found in almost every continent but is highly endemic in Central Asia, Eastern Europe, Northern Africa, Mediterranean countries, Middle East and Southern America [2]. CE occurs predominantly in communities which raise livestock and keep dogs for guarding and herding. A pastoral occupation, dog ownership, poor education, age, sex and drinking water source are known as potential risk factors [3]. Estimates from 2006 suggest that CE is globally responsible for the loss of 1 – 3 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) every year [2]. Furthermore, CE is estimated to cost \$3 billion in treatment and losses in the livestock industry [2]. Human CE incidence and prevalence rates are found to be higher than 50 cases per 100,000 person-years and 5-10% respectively, as seen in endemic regions of Peru, Argentina, east Africa and China [4]. Studies of the mitochondrial DNA sequences of *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* have identified several different genotypes. These include *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (s.s.) (G1 and G3), *E. canadensis* cluster [G6/7, G8, G10, proposed to be split into *E. intermedium* (G6/7), *E. borealis* (G8), and *E. canadensis* (G10)]; *E. ortleppi* (G4); *E. equinus* (G5); and *E. felidis* [5]. The sheep G1 strain is found in 90% of human cases [6] and is the strain this project will be focusing on.

CE is considered a neglected tropical disease by the WHO. Even though effective tools for control are available, this zoonosis remains endemic in many regions of South American countries such as Argentina, Peru, Chile and Uruguay. Between the period of January 2009 and December 2014, Peru, Chile, Uruguay, Argentina, and Brazil reported a total of 29,559 new cases of human CE [7]. *E. granulosus* s.s. (G1) is the prominent genotype identified in these regions. [8]

Distribution of *Echinococcus granulosus* and cystic echinococcosis, worldwide, 2011

The boundaries and names shown and the designations used on this map do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the World Health Organization concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Dotted lines on maps represent approximate border lines for which there may not yet be full agreement. © WHO 2012. All rights reserved

Data Source: World Health Organization
Map Production: Control of Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTD)
World Health Organization

Figure. 1 – The distribution of *E. granulosus* around the world, showing areas that are considered highly endemic. [9]

1.2 – *E. granulosus sensu lato*

1.2.1 - Life Cycle and Transmission

The life cycle of *E. granulosus sensu lato* (s.l.) involves a definitive host (dogs and other canids) and an intermediate host (ungulates). The definitive host becomes infected via the consumption of a cyst in the organ of hydatid-carrying livestock, often as a result of the feeding of infested offal by owners [7,8]. Once ingested, these cysts release protoscoleces that attach to the small intestine wall whereupon they mature into adult worms, with the process typically taking 4-6 weeks. Adult worms in dogs are estimated to live between 6 to 22 months, with each dog carrying thousands of worms [12]. The adult parasite will shed one to four gravid proglottides [13], each containing up to hundreds of eggs, excreted in the faeces and contaminating the environment [14,15] on average every 15 days [13]. *E. granulosus* eggs are shown to survive for up to 3 years in the right conditions [16], however at temperatures of 7°C and 21°C the eggs can only survive up to a year and a month respectively [14]. Evidence from epidemiological studies suggest that the definitive host can acquire resistance against infection naturally [17]. A model by Torgerson [18] indicates there is herd immunity in dogs in the presence of high infection pressure.

When ingested by an intermediate host via contaminated grass, water and soil, these eggs mature into metacestodes contained within hydatid cysts. These cysts are fluid-filled, spherical, unilocular cysts that consist of an inner germinal layer of cells supported by a characteristic acidophilic-staining, acellular, laminated membrane of variable thickness [19]. Each infected sheep develops 4.2 cysts on average with a range from 1-16 [20,21], each cysts growing between 1 – 5cm per year [22,23]. Only 45-50% of cysts are found to produce protoscoleces [14,24] and 52-88% of all protoscoleces are found to be able to mature into an adult worm in the intestine of a definitive host [25,26]. An infected sheep stays infected unless they receive treatment in the form of deworming [14].

Cystic Echinococcosis *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato*

Figure. 2 - Diagram illustrating the lifecycle of the cystic echinococcosis tapeworm and the stages at which different hosts can become infected, reproduced from [27].

1.2.2 - Human Clinical manifestations/features

Humans are considered accidental intermediate host, infected by the faecal-oral route through either direct contact with an infected dog, or via the ingestion of food, water or soil contaminated with egg infested faeces. After infection, an incubation period follows, with eggs releasing oncospheres which penetrate the intestinal wall. Oncospheres can develop into cysts on various organs, most commonly the liver or lungs, via the portal venous system [28].

Cysts growth rate varies from 0-10mm per year. These cysts are composed of two layers. An inner membrane which is nucleated and an outer membrane which is acellular. The immune system also responds by producing a calcified fibrous layer around the cyst which can be visualised in imaging studies. Cysts on multiple organs have been found in 10-15% of patients [1]. 20-40% of individuals have either multiple organ involvement or multiple cysts [29]. In 65% of cases, the cyst develops on the liver and in 25% of cases the cyst is found on the lungs. Cysts can develop on other organs as well such as kidney, bone, spleen and heart [12].

Due to the long incubation period, CE can develop asymptotically for many years undetected. It is often believed that infection is acquired during childhood, especially for infections of the liver or lung, with detection occurring in adulthood, however this concept has been contested [30]. The cysts become symptomatic depending on size, type (based on the WHO CE cyst classification [31]), numbers, secondary infection, presence of rupture and locations, as they can cause pain or discomfort by exerting pressure to the surrounding tissue. Cysts are classified by the WHO which includes types: CI, CE1, CE2, CE3A, CE3B, CE4, CE5. These types are divided into 3 groups: The active group (CE1, CE2, CE3b) describe cysts that are developing and fertile, Transitional group (CE3a) with cysts starting to degenerate, usually containing viable protoscoleces, and Inactive group (CE4, CE5): degenerated or partially or completely calcified cysts that are unlikely to be fertile. Cysts located in

locations such as the brain or the eye can become symptomatic earlier and are more often diagnosed in children. Symptoms of CE differ depending on the location and condition of the cysts; however, common aspecific symptoms include nausea and vomiting. The rupture of the cyst can induce symptoms such as an allergic reaction ranging from mild to fatal anaphylaxis [1].

1.2.3 - Diagnosis

Diagnosis of human CE is elicited from patient history, presentation of a cyst-like mass, serology and imaging [32]. History of contact with sheepdogs in regions where CE is known to be endemic, combined with examination of cystic content under a microscope can confirm a diagnosis. Diagnostic methods include ultrasonography, computerised tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). In recent years abdominal ultrasonography has become the gold standard diagnostic tool for widespread screening due to its low cost, availability [33] and sensitivity of 93-98% [34]. Diagnosis from serum studies in humans has shown to have low sensitivity and only 40% of patients show abnormal results for liver enzyme tests [1]. Serological testing is available such as the detection of IgG antibodies to the cystic fluid antigens using ELISA or immunoblots which have a sensitivity of 84% [34] and specificity of 98% [35]. The results of active and past infection are however indistinguishable and early highly active and late dead cyst stages often present seronegative.

E. granulosus prevalence in dogs is often used as part of surveillance programmes to elicit the prevalence and burden of the disease in endemic regions. The gold standard for diagnosis in dogs is necropsy with a sensitivity exceeding 97% [36]. Purging using arecoline can also produce highly reliable results (with a sensitivity range of 40-75% [36]). However, the drug has side effects such as oral squamous cell carcinoma and genotoxicity. Furthermore, it is very hard to implement as it requires dogs to be taken to purge sites. To overcome this limitation a combination of copro-PCR and copro-antigen detection ELISA can be used instead, faecal samples can be collected in the field making it very practical for the surveillance of a large dog population [37]. Copro-PCR is more often used for epidemiological studies. Copro-antigen has a sensitivity of 78-100%, and a specificity of 85-95% [36] and is shown to be detectable during the early course of infection [38]. The sensitivity of copro-PCR has proven to be quite low at <40% [39]. The most effective approach to wide scale screening for canids has been suggested to test samples with copro-ELISA and confirm positivity with PCR [36].

Domesticated ungulates can be diagnosed using ultrasound and necropsy [40]. Necropsy requires well equipped abattoirs and can produce a large proportion of false positives caused by unspecified granulomas, fatty degeneration, abscesses, etc. False negative diagnoses can be caused due to small intraparenchymal cysts. There have also been many challenges developing an effective serological diagnostic test for the detection of CE, despite a number of efforts. This is due to problems with insensitivity and cross reactions between *E. granulosus* and other cestodes [41].

1.2.4 - Treatment

The main objective of treatment in humans is to eliminate the germinal layer and currently this can be achieved through four different options: surgical, medical (parasitostatic drugs), percutaneous and "watch and wait". The method of treatment chosen is often dictated by the number of cysts present, the degree of the organ involved in the cysts [42], cyst type and size [32]. Figure 3 shows the preferred treatment based on cyst type and size with risk of complications. A curative approach is considered to be partial or total cystectomy without cystic contamination of the abdomen [4]. Pericystectomy is the common procedure used, but capitonnage, marsupialization, simple drainage and resection of the involved organ can also be used [43]. Surgical risks specifically associated with CE surgery include anaphylaxis and secondary recurrence. Operative mortality risks range from 0.5-4% but increases with repetition [44].

Chemotherapy using benzimidazole compounds (mainly albendazole but also mebendazole) is recommended generally for patients with smaller cysts. One-third of patients treated with said drugs have shown complete disappearance of cysts with no recurrence [45]. Furthermore, 30-50% show signs of cysts size reduction and removal of symptoms, but unfortunately 20-40% of cases do not respond well [44]. Cases with small isolated cysts respond best, those with presence of daughter cysts, thick or calcified surroundings react less positively.

One approach for percutaneous treatment of hydatid cysts follow the lettering of the acronym PAIR: Percutaneous puncture using sonographic guidance, aspiration of substantial amounts of liquid contents, injection of protoscolicidal agent for at least 15 minutes, and finally re-aspiration [46]. PAIR is indicated for patients who refuse to or cannot undergo surgery and have single or multiple cysts located in their liver, abdominal cavity, spleen, kidney, and bones. Complications of the procedure include secondary infection, recurrence, and acute allergic reactions. PAIR is not recommended for pulmonary cysts as they frequently incur complications [44].

The “watch and wait” approach is used for any inactive cysts. The idea is to monitor the cysts and only engage in active intervention if the need arises (such as signs of growth or rupturing) [32].

Figure. 3 – Assignments of treatment and risk of complications in relation to CE cyst stage and size [47].

Treatment of dogs is carried out via anthelmintic dosing using praziquantel. An effective recombinant vaccine antigen (EG95) is available for the intermediate host, which has proved to provide 96 – 98% protection from infection [48].

1.2.5 - Prevention and control method

The original successful control programme for CE was that in Iceland that started in the 1860s. At the time, it was found that around one in six of the population was afflicted by a hydatid cyst. By the 1950s echinococcosis was considered eradicated from Iceland. Other successful control programmes are also well known such as those in New Zealand and Tasmania. Since then the transmission of CE has been well understood; Many methods of Echinococcosis control and prevention were established and deemed to be effective due to these successful programmes, and many new approaches have become more accessible in the last decades.

Health education programmes have always been a major part of CE prevention: making sure that the general population is aware of the disease and what they can do to avoid infection such as washing hands after handling dogs, and avoiding food and water that could be contaminated with dog faeces [4]. Other established efforts to control CE transmission include reduction of home slaughter of sheep and feeding of offal to dogs, and building new infrastructure for the safe slaughter of sheep [49].

Ultrasonic screening of the population is a good strategy for the active screening for cysts before they develop further and become symptomatic [50].

Dogs are screened using copro-PCR, copro-ELISA or arecoline purge testing as part of the surveillance and monitoring strategy. Stray dogs have also been speculated to contribute to the spread of the disease, with many policies including neutering or other forms of stray dog population control. According to the Torgerson et al., the best course of intervention is a combination of sheep vaccination with a coverage of 75% and anthelmintic treatment for dogs on a 6-monthly basis; This method is estimated by models to reduce prevalence in both intermediate and definitive hosts to low levels. If only anthelmintic treatment is available as a control measure, the treatment intervals should be reduced to a 3-monthly basis [14].

Livestock screening is also available using serological tests and ultrasound but lacks sensitivity as mentioned previously. This is often more resource demanding compared to screening dogs in an agricultural setting due to the large number of samples required to represent the population in a farm. Culling of aged sheep can reduce prevalence as hydatid cysts are more commonly found in older sheep. The EG95 recombinant antigen vaccine has been used in multiple prevention and control programmes in the past. In China, this vaccine has been found to induce about 85% of protection against infection for 12 months in sheep. Two injections are needed at least one month apart to establish and boost the immunity, and further injections are required following 6-12 months to provide prolonged resistance to infection [48].

1.3 - Mathematical modelling

Mathematical modelling has been used to simulate disease transmission and provide insight into the impact of possible control strategies. Mathematical models that calculate and simulate the transmission of Cystic echinococcosis have existed since the 1980s [51]. Since then, the biological processes behind transmission dynamics have not changed, yet as evidenced by the continuing prevalence of CE in many regions, there are additional obstacles to overcome. This is often due to the fact that CE is endemic in nations and regions that are rural, outside the range of resources and the scope of attention from policymakers; Due to a long incubation period and often subtle symptoms, it is not a very attractive disease for pharmaceutical companies or governments to focus on [52]. It can take years before signs of improvement are seen following control measures that are put in place.

1.3.1 - Population-Based versus Individual-Based approaches

Two distinct types of modelling approaches are generally considered for disease transmission models, population-based models and individual-based models. Both these approaches share entities that dictate how they function: Individuals that influence the ecosystem and parameters that can be measured, each with a temporal element [53]. However, these approaches differ on the fundamental relationship between entities that are simulated, and the level of detail at which the focus is placed upon.

The most common type of population-based model for infectious disease epidemiology is the compartmental model, which places individuals into compartments and dictates how each compartment influences each other, which is represented mathematically using ordinary differential equations [54].

Figure. 4 – A basic structure of a population-based SIR model which demonstrates the compartments and the flow of which individuals will transition between compartments. βSI represents the transmission rate at which the susceptible become infected and γI represents the recovery rate of those infected moving to the recovered group. In this case the recovered do not become susceptible to the infection again, reproduced from [55].

These compartments thus group the population into categories and therefore individual behaviours cannot be explicitly accounted for. Populations are usually assumed to be homogenous and well mixed, although extensions exist, for example using sub-populations, to simulate more heterogeneous subgroups [56]. Many variations of the compartmental model exist for infectious diseases that encapsulate the different stages of the disease in individuals. For example, the susceptible/infected/recovered (SIR) model consisting 3 compartments: A susceptible population consisting of individuals that can contract the disease, an infected (and infectious) population consisting of individuals with the disease, and finally those recovered from the disease and incapable of contracting it again, Figure 4. This simple model, in a closed population of a fixed size N , is defined by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dS}{dt} &= \frac{-\beta SI}{N} \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \frac{\beta SI}{N} - \gamma I \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \gamma I\end{aligned}$$

With β representing the transmission rate and γ the recovery rate. These types of models have been used extensively to advise on policy for both endemic diseases and during outbreaks, for example during the 2001 foot-and-mouth disease epidemic in the UK [57]. As mentioned above, the main disadvantage of these models is that they cannot describe the heterogeneity of each separate individual organism. The assumption that the population is homogeneous in a compartment can prove to be simplistic, as it does not take into account individual variation that can cause major changes in the course of an infection [58].

Individual-based models on the other hand describe and simulate autonomous individuals within different environments, where they can interact with each other or the environment itself. Each individual will contain characteristics, such as age or infection status, which will change over time and/or due to “actions” the individual takes within the model [59]. This level of detail allows to account for heterogeneous mixing of populations, with the major limitation of these models being that they can be computationally intensive, thus taking a long time to run to completion. Similarly to population-based models, individual-based models have been used to inform policy for a variety of infectious diseases, such as various strains of influenza, Ebola, measles and HPV. [56]. Generally, the aim is to use the simplest models that can provide an answer to the research question being considered (Ockham’s razor), thus population-based approaches are usually preferred. However, as disease prevalence decreases and complexity of the interactions between the different hosts increase, a stochastic individual-based approach can better reproduce the biological processes being studied.

Models that try to simulate a system and make predictions can be deterministic, stochastic or include elements of both. A deterministic model will output results devoid of any involvement of randomness, thus determined entirely by the model parameters. Running these types of models multiple times with the same parameter values will always provide the same result. In contrast, a stochastic model incorporates a level of inherent randomness to account for any uncertainties from the data and the disease process being modelled. This type of model will generate a range of results, even with the same (fixed) model parameters. It is important to note that deterministic models can still account for

parameter uncertainty, when a range or a distribution, rather than a single value, is provided for certain model parameters.

1.3.2 – State of the art for CE Models

Since the first mathematical model on transmission dynamics of CE [51] many more models of the Taeniidae family have been developed [60]. In this section, I will concisely go over major existing models on CE and discuss the main gaps within the literature.

The original model on CE by Roberts et al. from 1986 [51] is a force-of-infection (FOI) model fitted to age-prevalence and age-abundance from New-Zealand. Force-of-infection models focus on trying to calculate the rate at which susceptible individuals transition into infected individuals. The model uses an integrodifferential equation model to achieve the equilibrium prevalence of the disease. In other words, it uses mathematical equations to explain the dynamics of transmission with the aim of reaching an equilibrium that can explain the prevalence reported in New Zealand. The model is mainly deterministic with stochastic elements.

Torgerson et al. [14] developed a deterministic FOI model based on integrodifferential equations. This model was developed to simulate different control options such as vaccinations in sheep, health education programmes and anthelmintic treatment in dogs. The model is heavily based on the assumptions made in the model by Roberts et al. but is expanded to simulate an immunity within the definitive host and see what effect that would have on the equilibrium prevalence.

More recently, Huang et al. [61] developed a model in China in 2011. It is quite unique as a model for *E. granulosus* as it is an agent-based, stochastic model. It was developed to study the dynamics of a small community. Huang et al. simulated the control strategies suggested in the Torgerson et al. model for comparison of its efficiency. The outcomes from the IBM were comparable but differed slightly. The 6-monthly dosing of anthelmintic in dogs produced an infection rate equilibrium of 20% in the Torgerson et al. model compared to 28% in the IBM. Finally, while in Torgerson et al. the combination of 6-monthly dosing and sheep vaccination achieved an infection rate of zero in 15 years, in with the IBM, an infection rate of <1% within 20 years was estimated.

Two models were developed in China around the same time by Wang et al. [62] and Wu et al. [63] in 2013. Both are compartmental, deterministic, population-based models. A major difference between these two models is that the one by Wang et al. contains an additional compartment for humans to estimate a latent status post-infection. This model was expanded upon in 2015 [64] by the same team to include an approach to estimate egg contamination dynamics in the environment. This extension incorporates infection delays between hosts with different distribution functions chosen to reflect differences in the range of host movements such as livestock or human [60].

1.4 – Aims and objectives of mace

As mentioned above, the only individual-based model available for CE is limited to a small population in China. There is a clear lack of a model calibrated for settings in South America, that accounts for individual heterogeneity and can also reflect the heterogeneous landscape of prevalence where programmes have been ongoing for many years and is currently on its path to Elimination. Moreover, a portfolio approach accounting for costs and investment opportunities for alternative control strategies is lacking. In MACE, we will be developing an individual-based model that will be able to simulate the transmission of CE on a wide range of settings in South America. A Geostatistical model will be developed alongside to estimate prevalence of CE at fine spatial scales. When combining both approaches, I will be able to help inform nation-wide surveillance programmes at small spatial scales (below state level). I will also conduct an economic analysis to inform the financial burden of CE, which will be used as part of a cost-effectiveness analysis for a range of possible control interventions. An elicitation questionnaire will also be conducted to assess the value that stakeholders place on surveillance sensitivity and detection of incident CE cases. All this combined will allow to generate realistic control scenarios, accounting for the epidemiology of the disease, the economic viability of the intervention proposed and their likely acceptance by stakeholders.

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